

THOT THEORY OF TONE

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Hausa. Analytical report on the tonal system

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This report relies primarily on Paul Newman's (2000) analysis of the Hausa tonal system, supplemented by additional information on Hausa grammar and illustrative examples from the work of Jaggar (2001).

1. General information

Hausa (ISO 639-3: hau, Glottocode: haus1257) is a West Chadic language of the Afro-Asiatic family spoken in Northern Nigeria and southern areas of the Republic of Niger. There are also speakers of Hausa in Ghana and in the Blue Nile area of Sudan (Newman 2000: 1). Hausa has a number of dialects such as western Hausa (e.g. Sokoto and Tahoua), eastern Hausa (e.g. Kano and Zinder), Katsina, Maradi, and others (Newman 2000: 1). This report is based on the dialect of Kano.

2. Segmental phonology

2.1. Phonemic inventory

2.1.1. Vowels

Hausa has ten monophthongal vowel phonemes: five short vowels and five long vowels, see Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Hausa monophthongal short vowels

i		u
	e	o
		a

Table 2. Hausa monophthongal long vowels

i:		u:
	e:	o:
		a:

Hausa vowel inventory also includes two oral diphthongs: /ai/ and /au/¹ and three nasal diphthongs /aN/, /iN/, and /uN/ (where the nasal element manifests some vocalic features) (Newman 2000: 405).

In the Hausa scholarly transcription, the vowel length is indicated with a macron, as in <ā>, or with double letters <aa>. Another way of identifying vowel length is the presence of circumflex above a vowel symbol, as in <â>. In this case, the circumflex symbol signifies a Falling tone that occurs only on heavy syllables including the CV: syllable type. In this report, I designate the vowel length with a colon, e.g. a:

2.1.2. Consonants

Standard Hausa has 32 consonant phonemes listed in Table 3.

¹ Historically, two additional oral diphthongs have been attested in Hausa: */iu/ and */ui/. The diphthong */ui/ were monophthongized to /i:/, while */iu/ were monophthongized to /u:/ (Newman 2000: 403). Some linguists synchronically recognize /ui/ as a third diphthong which appears in syllables traditionally written with a labialized velar onset followed by a long vowel /i:/, as in *túk^wi:tfi:* ~ *túkui:tfi:* ‘small gift’ (Newman, p.c.).

Table 3. Hausa consonant inventory

			Labial	Palatalized labial	Alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Labialized velar	Palatalized velar	Laryngeal	
Obstr.	stop	voiceless			t		k	k ^w	k ^j		
		voiced	b		d		g	g ^w	g ^j		
		glottolized	ɓ		ɗ	y	ƙ	ƙ ^w	ƙ ^j	ʔ	
	affr.	voiceless				tʃ					
		voiced				dʒ					
		glottolized			ts						
	fric.	voiceless	f	f ^ɓ	s	ʃ				h	
		voiced			z						
	Sonor.		nasal	m		n					
			lateral			l					
flap					ɾ						
tap/roll					r						
glide						j		w			

In this report, I replace certain Hausa scholarly transcription symbols with their phonemic counterparts. These symbols are denoted within angle brackets <a>, while phonemic transcription is provided between two slashes /a/. The following Hausa scholarly transcription symbols are represented by their corresponding phonemic equivalents: <fy> → /f^ɓ/, <r> → /ɾ/, <ř> → /r/, <'y> → /y/, <y> → /j/, <c> → /tʃ/, <j> → /dʒ/, <kw> → /k^w/, <gw> → /g^w/, <ƙw> → /ƙ^w/, <ky> → /k^j/, <gy> → /g^j/, and <ƙy> → /ƙ^j/.

Note that sequences of identical consonants are found only across a syllable boundary, as in *dʒábbà*: ‘sleeveless robe’ → CVC.CV:

2.2. Prosodic units

2.2.1. Syllable and mora

Tone-bearing unit (TBU) in Hausa is a mora. This analysis is supported by the fact that a sequence of H and L tonemes can occur on a heavy syllable, namely CV: or CVC, but it cannot occur on a light syllable. Any type of consonant (sonorant or obstruent) is allowed in the coda

of a CVC syllable, e.g. *bêlbé:là:* ‘cattle egret’, *kàttá:* ‘huge (pl.)’, *zík* ‘zipper’, *g^jâffá:* ‘sides’, *kâr* ‘don’t’.

Paul Newman (2000) analyses a syllable as a TBU. According to his analysis, the tone inventory includes three tonemes: High, Low and Falling. Each of them can be carried by one syllable, e.g. *wàndó:* ‘trousers’ and *jâ:ɽá:* ‘children’. In this report, a falling contour is analysed as a sequence of H and L tonemes. As it was mentioned above, falling contours occur only on heavy (bimoraic) syllables. The L tone of the falling contour can be a result of vowel deletion, as in *kádà* vs. *kâr* ‘don’t’. The L tone of the falling contour can be part of another morpheme, as in *wàndó:* ‘trousers’ + -̀̀ (DEF.MSC.SG) → *wàndón* ‘the trousers’, see Section 3.2. for more information.

Hausa has three syllable types: CV, CV: and CVC. A CV: syllable consists of a consonantal onset and a nucleus that includes either a long vowel or a diphthong.

The nasal *n* that occurs in Can, Cin and Cun syllables is considered to be part of a complex nucleus rather than part of a coda. This can be confirmed by the similarity of the morphophonological behaviour of *an*, *in*, *un* and diphthongs /ai/, /au/. For example, vowel-initial suffixes replace the nucleus of the final syllable of the root when it is represented by a long vowel (1), diphthong *au* or *ai* (2) or *an*, *in* or *un* (3, 4), but when a word-final syllable is the CVC type, it remains intact (5).

- (1) *tá:g-o:gì:* ‘windows’ (*tá:gà:* ‘window’-PL)
- (2) *kámfo:* *mátà* ‘the hell with the underpants!’ (*kámfai* ‘underpants’ + -o:\H (EXCM) + *mátà* ‘to her’)
- (3) *tángar-à:jé:* ‘chinawares’ (*tángarán* ‘chinaware’-PL)
- (4) *hámso:* *mátà* ‘So what about fifty!’ (*hàmsín* ‘fifty’ + -o:\H (EXCM) + *mátà* ‘to her’)
- (5) *té:bùr-ó:rí:* ‘tables’ (*té:bùr* ‘table’-PL)

Syllable weight plays an important role in the Hausa phonology and morphology. For example, the form of the verbalizing suffix *-ata* / *-a:ta* depends on the weight of the preceding syllable: *-ata* comes after a heavy syllable, while *-a:ta* comes after a light syllable, e.g. *tsò:r-átà* ‘be afraid (gr3)’ (< *tsò:ɽó:* ‘fear’), *fùs-á:tà* ‘become angry (gr3)’ (< *fú:fí:* ‘anger’). Note that the tonal melody and the final vowel of a derived verbal form with *-ata* / *-a:ta* are determined by a verb grade (see Jaggar 2001: 276 for more details). Some correlations between syllable weight and tone are also attested in Hausa. For example, disyllabic intransitive verbs of the grade 3 with

the final vowel *-a* have the L-H melody when the first syllable is light and the H tonal melody when the first syllable is heavy, as in *tùmá* ‘jump’ (CV.CV) and *gítma* ‘grow up’ (CVC.CV).

2.2.2. Foot

Leben (1997, 2001) postulates a tonal foot that is the prosodic word of the tone assignment in Hausa loanwords from English. However, his study only focuses on a limited part of lexicon and does not clarify the question of the pertinence of foot in Hausa. In my understanding, there is not enough evidence to postulate existence of foot in this language.

2.2.3. Word form and root

Most of underived and uninflected words in Hausa consist of two, three or four syllables. Longer words usually contain derivational or inflectional morphemes, or are borrowed from Arabic. Monosyllabic words are mostly pronouns and functional morphemes (e.g. *mú*: ‘we’, *dà* ‘and/with, that’), ideophones (e.g. *fát* ‘very white’), there are also some verbs and nouns (e.g. *bí* ‘follow’, *sá*: ‘put’, *já*u ‘today’, *kʷái* ‘egg’) and one adjective (*dzá*: ‘red’).

A word form can comprise:

- (i) a root, e.g. *wàndó*: ‘trousers’, *báki*: ‘black.SG’, *bí* ‘follow’;
- (ii) a root plus prefixes and/or suffixes, e.g. *dzá:ká*: ‘donkey (f.)’ (*dzá:kí*: ‘donkey (m.)’ + *-á*: (FEM)), *wàndôn* ‘the trousers’ (*wàndó*: ‘trousers’ + *-n* (DEF.MSC.SG)), *mádo:gaɽi*: ‘prop’ (*ma-* (INSTR) + *dó:gaɽá*: ‘lean on’ + *-í*:H (INSTR)). Note that word form can include only one prefix and more than one suffix, as in *dàkakkú*: ‘pounded (pl)’ (*dákà* ‘pound’ + *-aC_iC_e:\LHH* (PST.PART) + *-u:\LH* (PL));
- (iii) partially and fully reduplicated roots, e.g. *bùguzunzum* ‘fat and ungainly (m./f.)’, *bùguzum-bùguzum* ‘fat and ungainly (pl.)’, *zàzzá:fá*: ‘very hot’ (*zá:fí*: ‘heat’ + reduplication (INT) + *-á:\LHH* (INT)).

A whole word form or its part can function as a prosodic word onto which a tonal melody is mapped, see Sections 4.2 and 6.1.2.

3. Tonal inventory

3.1. Character of tonal system

Hausa has a level-tone system that includes H and L pitch levels.

There is a tonal contour HL which appears on heavy syllables only.

3.2. Inventory of tonemes

There are two tonemes in Hausa: H and L. The following criteria for determining the tonemic status of H can be provided:

- The Tonal Morpheme Criterion: a H tone can be a tonal grammatical morpheme, e.g. the Plural marker -o:C_i:\H, see Section 7;
- The Floating Criterion: a H tone can float, see Section 3.3;
- The Activity Criterion: a H tone is involved into the Tonal Polarity rule, see Section 6.1.

The following criteria for determining the tonemic status of L can be provided:

- The Floating Criterion: a L tone can float, see Section 3.3;
- The Activity Criterion: a L tone is involved into the Tonal Polarity rule, see Section 6.1.

The Falling tone can be analysed as both a unitary contour included into the tonal inventory and as a combination of H and L, see (Newman 2000: 597). The choice of the analysis may depend on historical and psycholinguistic aspects of Hausa. In this report, a falling tone is analysed as a sequence of two tonemes, H and L. There are several arguments in favour of this analysis:

- falling contours do not occur on a single TBU, viz. a mora; they are only found on heavy syllables (i.e., the Extensibility Criterion is not applicable);
- the L tone of the falling contour can result from vowel deletion, as in *kádà* → *kâr* ‘don’t’;
- falling contours is composed of levels which are available in Hausa as tonemes (i.e., the Non-Compositionality Criterion is not applicable).

A falling contour can be found in a number of loanwords, e.g. *šât* ‘shirt’, *tôn* ‘ton’, *řàfalî* ‘referee’, *bà:silîn* ‘vaseline’, *gàrantî* ‘guarantee’. In this case, the falling contour can represent an adaptation of the English stress (Leben 2001, Newman 2000: 606). Finally, a falling contour can be historically related to a deleted segment, as in *mùtûm* (from *mùtûmî*) ‘man, person’, *gáùdzí* (from *gá:wùdzí*) ‘fool, jester’.

Tone in Hausa has a lexical and grammatical function. Lexical minimal pairs are not very common, e.g. *wújà* ‘neck’ vs. *wùjá* ‘trouble’, *górà* ‘staff, bamboo’ vs. *gòrá* ‘large gourd’, *bà:bá* ‘dad’ vs. *bá:bà* ‘mom, aunt’, *kái* ‘you (m.)’ vs. *kâi* ‘head’. There are also toneless morphemes, e.g. the copulae *ne*: (MSC.SG/PL) and *tfe*: (FEM.SG) that always takes a tone opposite to the preceding one (Sections 4.3 and 6.1.1).

3.3. Floating tones

Floating L and H tones are attested in Hausa.

3.5. Upstep

Upstep is not attested in Hausa.

3.6. Other suprasegmental features of tonemes apart from pitch

Other suprasegmental features of tonemes apart from pitch are not attested in Hausa.

4. Tonotactics

4.1. Tonal span limits

A tonal span can be a mora, a syllable or several syllables.

The minimal size of a tonal span is a mora. For instance, the monosyllabic noun *ɟàt* ‘shirt’ carries two tonemes, and its subdivision into tonal spans can be conventionally represented as follows: [H ɟa][L t].

When both morae of a heavy syllable carry identical tones, it is counted as one toneme, as in *kúdzè:rá:* ‘chair’ [H ku][L dʒe:][H ra:], *wàhálà:* ‘trouble’ [L wa][H ha][L la:] and *má:làm* ‘teacher’ [H ma:][L lam].

A tonal span can include more than one syllable. In this case, the rule of tonal melody mapping from right to left within one prosodic word allows us to define the boundaries of prosodic words and tonal spans. Specifically:

- when all syllables of one prosodic word carry identical tones, this prosodic word carries a single toneme. For example, two H tones form one H toneme in *gída:* ‘house’, see also (12, 13).
- A sequence of identical tones at the left edge of a prosodic word also forms one toneme. For instance, in *gá:farà:* ‘forgiveness’, the H-L tonal melody is applied from the right edge to the left, with the H toneme extending over the syllables *fà* and *ga:*, see (14)-(16) for more examples.

(12) *fito:* ‘come out’ (*fitá* ‘go out’ + -o:\H (VEN)) [H fito:]

(13) *tá:tsumi:jo:ji:* ‘riddles’ (*tà:tsumi:nìjá:* ‘riddle’ + -o:C_i:\H (PL)) [H tá:tsumi:jo:ji:]

(14) *ɽí:gunà:* ‘gowns’ (*ɽì:gá:* ‘gown (SG)’ + -una:\HL (PL)) [H ɽi:gu][L na:]

(15) *ɽà:nakú:* ‘days’ (*ɽá:ma:* ‘day’ + -aki:\LH (PL)) [L ɽa:na][H ku:]

(16) *là:fi:jájjé:* ‘healthy’ (*lá:fi:jà:* ‘health’ + -aC_iC_ie:\LHH (ABSTR)) [L la:fi][H jaj][H je:]

A sequence of two identical tones at the right edge of a prosodic word is treated as two tonemes, as the right-to-left mapping rule cannot be applied here. For example, in the noun *ɽàgò:gó* ‘watch’, the L-H-H tonal melody includes three distinct tonemes: L, H, and H, see also (16).

One word form can include more than one tonal melody and, therefore, more than one prosodic word. This type of word form includes a tonally independent prefix and/or suffix. Below, I provide two examples, where the H-toned Agentive prefix *má-* or the H-toned Feminine suffix *-á:* share a common boundary with a H-toned syllable of the neighbouring morpheme. Since sequential H tones are part of different tonal melodies, they belong to different prosodic words and, therefore, to different tonal spans, for example:

- The word *dó:guwá:* ‘long (f.)’ (*dó:go:* ‘long (m.)’ + *-á:* (FEM)) has three H tones. I analyze this form as having two H tonemes, viz. [H do:gu][H wa:], since these two morphemes do not interact tonally. In particular, there is no replacive melody imposed by the Feminine marker *-á:* or by the lexical H melody of *dó:go:*.³
- *máháifjájá:* ‘parent (f.)’ (*má-* (AGT) + *hàifá:* ‘give birth to’ + *ija:\HLH* (FEM.AGT)) includes four tonemes, viz. [H ma][H hai][L fi][H ja:], and *máfá:jíjájá:* ‘drinker (f.)’ (*má-* (AGT) + *já:* ‘drink’ + *ija:\HLH* (f.)) includes four tonemes, viz. [H ma][H ja:][L ji][H ja:]. The grammatical tonal melody connected to the suffix *-ija:\HLH* replaces the lexical tone of *hàifá:* ‘give birth to’ and *já:* ‘drink’ without extending onto the prefix *má-*.⁴

4.2. Tonal melodies

Hausa has a number of lexical or grammatical **tonal melodies**. For example, the noun *tɸò:ló:lò:* ‘tall and lanky (m.)’ carries the L-H-L lexical tonal melody, while the plural form of the noun *ɸí:gunà:* ‘gowns’ carries the H-L grammatical tonal melody associated with the plural suffix *-una:\HL* that replaces the L-H lexical tonal pattern of the singular form *ɸì:gá:* ‘gown’.

Tonal melodies are mapped onto a **prosodic word**. A prosodic word is a word form without the agentive prefix *má-*,⁵ the gentile prefix *bà-*, Feminine suffixes *-á:*⁶ and *-níjájá:*, the nominalization

³ Compare with the form *tɸò:ló:lùwá:* ‘tall and lanky (f.)’ (*tɸò:ló:lò:* ‘tall and lanky (m.)’ + *-á:* (f.)), which contains four tonemes (L, H, L, and H) and two tonal melodies (L-H-L and H). Both morphemes preserve their lexical melodies.

⁴ Compare these two examples with corresponding masculine Agentive forms *máhàifí:* ‘parent (m.)’ (*má-* (AGT) + *hàifá:* ‘give birth to’ + *-i:\LH* (MSC.AGT)) and *máfá:jí:* ‘drinker (m.)’ (*má-* (AGT) + *já:* ‘drink’ + *-i:\LH* (MSC.AGT)), where the initial L tone of *-i:\LH* does not spread on the Agentive prefix *má-* either.

⁵ Unlike the agentive prefix *má-*, the instrumental prefix *ma-* and the locative prefix *ma-* are included into the following prosodic word, e.g. *másalla:ɸí:* ‘mosque’ (*ma-* (LOC) + *sàllàtà:* ‘perform prayer’ + *i:\H* (MSC.LOC)), *màsallatái* ‘mosques’ (*ma-* (LOC) + *sàllàtà:* ‘perform prayer’ + *ai:\LH* (PL)).

More details on different lexical or grammatical tonal melodies are provided in Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2. The distribution of sequences of tonemes on one syllable is discussed in Section 4.2.3. Some melodies can also have two variants depending on the number of syllables within a prosodic word, see Section 4.2.4.

4.2.1. Lexical tonal melodies

A lexical tonal melody can include one, two or three tonemes, viz. H, L, H-L, L-H, H-L-H, L-H-L, L-H-H, and H-L-L, see Table 4. Sections 4.2.1.1 and 4.2.1.2 focuses on lexical tonal melodies on monosyllabic and polysyllabic prosodic words.

4.2.1.1. Tone melodies on monosyllabic prosodic words

Monosyllabic prosodic words can carry the H, L, or H-L tonal melody. Functional morphemes can carry H or L, e.g. *dà* ‘with, and’, *tá* ‘via’. If represented by a heavy syllable, it can also carry the H-L melody, e.g. *zá:* (Allative marker). Pronouns can carry H or L, e.g. *-tà* (3SG.FEM.POSS), *tá* (strong pronoun of 3SG.FEM.DO). Ideophones frequently carry H, but L and H-L are also found, e.g. *fés* ‘very (clean)’, *sùm* ‘describes an outburst of a bad smell’, *bíf* ‘sound of heavy object falling’. Monosyllabic verbs are commonly H-toned, e.g. *já:* ‘drink’. These H-toned verbs originally have a monosyllabic form. However, the H-L melody on a monosyllabic verb is also found, e.g. *sá:* ‘put’. These verbs have a reduced disyllabic form, e.g. *tfê:* ‘say’ (from *tfánè:*). Most monosyllabic nouns are represented by heavy syllables with the H-L melody, e.g. *wá:* ‘elder brother’. Only a few nouns carry either the H or L melody, e.g. *dá:* ‘son’, *sàu* ‘times’.

4.2.1.2. Tonal melodies on polysyllabic prosodic words

Underived polysyllabic prosodic words can carry the following tonal melodies: H, L, H-L, L-H, H-L-H, L-H-L, L-H-H, and H-L-L, e.g. *rá:na:* ‘day’, *dàlala* ‘in a slimy manner, viscously’, *gá:farà:* ‘forgiveness’, *mà:tá:* ‘wife’, *hánkàlí:* ‘intelligence’, *gùdúmà:* ‘hammer’, *ʔàgó:gó* ‘watch’, *ʔásfirìn* ‘aspirin’.⁸

Tonal melodies may have specific distributional properties:

- The L melody on disyllabic and trisyllabic underived prosodic words is infrequent, e.g. *fè:la* ‘proclamation’, *ʔàdudu* ‘large lidded woven basket’. It is commonly found on partially reduplicated words, e.g. *gà:dʒa:dʒa:* ‘filthy’, *dàlala* ‘in a slimy manner, viscously’.

⁸ The distribution of tonal melodies is not influenced by the syllable weight or other segmental characteristics of a prosodic word.

- The H melody on trisyllabic underived prosodic words occurs only on partially reduplicated words, e.g. *dánana* ‘very oily’, *bírbíri*: ‘Bruce’s fruit pigeon’.
- The L-H melody is infrequent on trisyllabic underived prosodic words, e.g. *tàfasá*: ‘a senna plant’.
- The melody H-L-L is also relatively uncommon, e.g. *tšírò:mà* ‘traditional title, prince’. This melody is commonly found on loanwords, e.g. *ʔásfirin* ‘aspirin’.

In addition, Hausa also has female nouns whose final H-toned vowel is related to the feminine suffix *-á*, e.g. *tà:tsú:nijá*: ‘riddle’, *tsá:mijá*: ‘tamarind’, *ʔámarjá*: ‘bride’. Even though these nouns are not considered as synchronically derived from a root and the feminine suffix *-á*, I will analyse the final H-toned vowel as a separate tonal melody.

4.2.2. Grammatical tonal melodies

Grammatical tonal melodies can include from one to four tonemes: H, L, H-L, L-H, H-L-H, L-H-L, L-H-H, H-L-L, and H-L-H-H, see Table 4. Most of grammatical melodies are associated with grammatical segmental morphemes, e.g. the suffix that creates abstract nouns *-aC_iC_ie*: is connected with the L-H-H melody, while the plural suffix *-aki*:\HLHH is connected with the H-L-H-H melody, see Examples (17) and (18) and Section 7.

(17) *là:fijájjé*: ‘healthy’ (*lá:fijà*: ‘health’ + *-aC_iC_ie*:\LHH (ABSTR))

(18) *ká:jàjjákí*: ‘loads’ (*ká:ja*: ‘load’ + reduplication + *-aki*:\HLHH (PL))

There is also at least one tonal melody that is not associated with any segmental morpheme and represents therefore purely tonal morphemes, viz. the imperative melody \LH, as in (19) and (20).

(19) *bàrì* ‘Leave!’ (*bá:rì* ‘leave’ + \LH (IMP))

(20) *kàrantá*: ‘Read (it)!’ (*ká:ràntá*: ‘read’ + \LH (IMP))

Jaggar (2001: 98) and Newman (2000: 368) postulate the abstract suffix *-e:C_ie:nija*:\LHHLH whose melody includes five tonemes L-H-H-L-H. I analyse this segmental sequence as two suffixes, namely the abstract suffix *-e:C_ie*:\LHH and the feminine suffix *-nijá*, as in (21) and (22). Thus, the abstract nouns derived according to this model consist of two prosodic words and, therefore, carry two tonal melodies: LHH and LH.

(21) *jà:rdzédzénijá*: ‘agreement’ (*jàrdá* ‘agree’ + *-e:C_ie*:\LHH (ABSTR) + *-nijá*: (FEM))

(22) *tšù:dédénijá*: ‘rubbing up against and pushing one other’ (*tšù:dá*: ‘knead’ + *-e:C_ie*:\LHH (ABSTR) + *-nijá*: (FEM))

4.2.3. Two tonemes on one syllable

On the surface level, Hausa does not allow sequences of L and H on one syllable. If L and H happen to be mapped on one syllable, this sequence is simplified either to H or to L, see Section 6.1.5 for more information.

Sequences of H and L on one heavy syllable are widely attested in Hausa. The sequence of HL is found on:

- monosyllabic prosodic words, e.g. *wâ:* ‘elder brother’. HL occur in loanwords *ʃât* ‘shirt’, *tôn* ‘ton’ as an adaptation of the English stress;
- on the last syllable of polysyllabic prosodic words: (i) due to segment deletion, e.g. *mùtùm* (from *mùtúmì*) ‘man, person’, (ii) in loanwords as an adaptation of the English stress, e.g. *bà:silín* ‘vaseline’, *gàrantî:* ‘guarantee’;
- on the first syllable of polysyllabic prosodic words due to segment deletion, e.g. *gáùdǝí:* (from *gá:wùdǝí*) ‘fool, jester’, *mântá:* ‘forget’ (historically trisyllabic form).

The sequence HL does not occur in the middle of a prosodic word. However, it can occur within one word form with multiple prosodic words, e.g. *kàràntá:wá:* ‘reading’ (*kàràntá:* ‘read’ + ⁻*wá:* (NMLZ)).

4.2.4. Tonal melodies variants

Hausa verbs are classified into eight lexico-derivative classes (or Grades). Grades 1, 2, and 3 are characterized by specific tone melodies of their verbs. In each Grade, the tonal melody has two variants depending on the number of syllables within a verb form. Thus, verbs of Grade 1 carry either a HL or HLH variant. The disyllabic Grade 1 verb *g^íá:ɽà:* ‘repair’ has a HL melody, while the trisyllabic Grade 1 verb *kámmàlá:* has a HLH melody. The HL melody can be replaced by the HLH melody when a trisyllabic verb is derived from a disyllabic one (and maintains the tonal melody). For example, it is observed in the case of pluractional reduplication. More information on tonal melody alternation is provided in Section 6.1.2.4.

4.3. Toneless syllables

In Hausa toneless syllables are represented

- by the copulae *ne:* (SG.MSC/PL) and *tfe:* (SG.FEM), see Section 6.1.1

- by weak object pronouns, see §6.1.1.⁹

The toneless syllables remain extratonal on the surface, they are not included into tonal spans. The toneless syllables take the tone opposite to the preceding tone.

4.4. Tonal phrases

A **tonal phrase in Hausa** is a fully reduplicated word form. Each part of reduplicated word has its own melody, viz. L-H, H-L, H-H, L-L, L-L or LH-LH, as in (21).

(23) *kíri:-kíri:* ‘brazenly’, *bàga:-bàga:* ‘floundering’, *bádza-bádza* ‘disorganized’, *bùja:-bùja:* ‘movement with a big gown’, *dǎgwàm-dǎgwàm* ‘incessantly’, *tìnkís-tìnkís* ‘hurrying along straight’

5. Stress and tone

5.1. Culminativity

Hausa tone is not culminative.

5.2. Stress

Hausa has no stress.

5.3. Positional prominence

Hausa does not have positional prominence.

5.4. Obligatoriness of tone

A word form in Hausa bears at least one toneme.

⁹ The Feminine marker *-a:* is traditionally analysed as toneless. In this report, I analyze the Feminine suffix *-á:* as H-toned when it forms feminine nouns and adjectives from their masculine counterparts. In locative nouns, the Feminine suffix *-a:* has an associated H tonal melody, e.g. *mákaɽanta:* ‘school’ (ma- (LOC) + *káɽàntá:* ‘read’ + *-a:\H* (FEM.LOC)). There is also a small group of nouns that end in a L-toned /a:/, e.g. *kíbijà:* ‘arrow’, *kúrwà:* ‘beetle’. However, these feminine forms are no longer segmentable into a root and the Feminine marker *-a:*.

6. Tonal and segmental rules

6.1. Tonal rules

6.1.1. Tonal polarity

The toneless copulae *ne:* (SG.MSC/PL) and *tfɛ:* (SG.FEM) take the tone opposite to the preceding one, as in (24) and (25). The tone of a copula is not considered as a toneme, since it is predicted by the tonal polarity rule.

(24) *ɔ̀:ɡá: tfɛ:* ‘It’s a gown’

(25) *mó:tà: tfɛ:* ‘It’s a car’

Hausa also has strong and weak object pronouns. Strong object pronouns are always H-toned and can be found after a verb with a final H or L tone, as in (26) and (27). Weak object pronouns always surface a L tone, only occurring after a verb with a final H tone. Therefore, weak object pronouns can be considered toneless, even though they never surface a H tone, see (28).

(26) *ná: dú:bà: jí* ‘I looked at it’ (ná: 1SG.PFV.NFOC + dú:bà: ‘look’ + jí 3SG.MSC)

(27) *ná: káràntá: jí* ‘I read it’ (ná: 1SG.PFV.NFOC + káràntá: ‘read’ + jí 3SG.MSC)

(28) *ná: tàmbajé: sù* ‘I asked them’ (ná: 1SG.PFV.NFOC + tàmbajé: ‘read.ACC’ + su 3PL)

6.1.2. Rules of tone mapping

6.1.2.1. General remarks

Tone mapping is the process of a tonal melody assignment to a prosodic word. A tonal melody is assigned from right to left. By default, one toneme of a tonal melody is assigned to one syllable of a prosodic word. For example, the imperative LH melody is assigned to the verb form *tá:fí* ‘get up’ in (29), while the HLH melody of the Plural suffix *-a:Ce:* is assigned to the form *bákà:ké:* in (30). However, the number of syllables within a prosodic word may not match with the number of tonemes within a tonal melody. These cases are discussed in the following sections.

(29) /tá:fí/

|tá:fí-LH|

get_up-IMP

‘Get up!’

(30) /bákà:ké:/

|báki:-a:Ce\HLH|

black.SG-PL

‘black (pl.)’

Tonal melody is mapped within a prosodic word. The prosodic word is a word form that does not include the agentive prefix *má-*, the gentile prefix *bà-*, Feminine suffixes *-á:* and *-nìjá:*, the nominalization suffix *-^Lwá:*, the proximal suffix *-^Lnán*, the distal suffix *-^Ltján*, and the definite articles *-n̄* (MSC.SG/PL) and *-r̄* (FEM.SG) which constitute separate prosodic words. The word form in (31) contains two prosodic words that carry two melodies, H and L-H. In (32), the word form includes two prosodic words with H-L-H and L-H tonal melodies. The word form in (33) is one prosodic word, as it does not include any tonally independent morpheme.

(31) /sáɾaunìjá/

|sáɾki:-nìjá:|

king-FEM

‘queen’

(32) /táttàunâ:wá:/

|táttàunâ:-^Lwá:|

discuss-NMLZ

‘discussing’

(33) /tá:go:gi/

|tá:gâ:-o:C_i:\H|

window.SG-PL

‘windows’

Tonal melody mapping can be accompanied by different processes, viz. tonal melody shift (Section 6.1.2.3), tonal melody replacement (Section 6.1.2.4), tonal melody alternation (Section 6.1.2.5), toneme extension (Section 6.1.2.6), contour tone formation (Section 6.1.2.7) and toneme deletion (Section 6.1.2.8). Tonal melody alternation, toneme extension, contour tone formation and toneme deletion take place when there are differences between the number of syllable within a prosodic word and the number of tonemes within a tonal melody.

6.1.2.2. Tonal melody shift

When a prosodic word is expanded, its tonal melody is re-assigned to that expanded word from right to left. The expansion of a prosodic word occurs in the Imperative construction when object pronouns integrate into the preceding verb form: the Imperative tonal melody L-H is mapped onto a verb root and the following object pronoun (34).

- (34) mà:ɾé: ‘slap’ + \LH (IMP) + -tà (3SG.FEM) →
mà:ɾé: ‘slap’ + -tà (3SG.FEM) + \LH (IMP) → mà:ɾé:tá ‘Slap her!’

6.1.2.3. Tonal melody replacement

Hausa has a number of morphemes whose tonal melody can replace another tonal melody. These morphemes (i) can be purely tonal (35) or (ii) can have both segmental and tonal components (36).

- (35) /tà:ʃí/
|tá:ʃí-\LH|
get_up-IMP
‘Get up!’
- (36) /bákà:ké:/
|báki:-a:Ce\HLH|
black.SG-PL
‘black (pl.)’

A grammatical tonal melody replaces a lexical melody, as in (37) and (38). If there is more than one grammatical melody, the most recent one replaces the preceding one.

- (37) /dàkáké:/
|dákà-aC_fC_fe:\LHH|
pound-PST.PART
‘pounded (sg)’
- (38) /dàkakkú:/

|dákà-aC_fC_fe:\LHH-u:\LH|

pound-PST.PART-PL

‘pounded (pl)’

6.1.2.4. Tonal melody alternation

Each verb class, so called verb Grade, has its own tonal melody (Section 8). Some of these melodies can have two variants depending on the number of syllables in the verb form. For example, disyllabic verbs of Grade 2 have a LH melody, as in *sàjá:* ‘buy’, while trisyllabic verbs of the same grade have a LHL melody, as in *tàimákà:* ‘help’. When a trisyllabic Grade 2 verb is derived from disyllabic one, it carries the LHL melody. This takes place in the pluractional form of verbs that are formed through the partial reduplication, e.g. the disyllabic Grade 2 verb *nè:má:* ‘look for’ whose LH melody changes to LHL in the pluractional form *nànné:mà:* ‘look for repeatedly’.

6.1.2.5. Toneme extension

Tonal melody extends from right to left. Toneme extension takes place when the number of syllables within one prosodic word exceeds the number of tonemes in a tonal melody. In this case, the initial toneme of the melody extends from right to left of a prosodic word. For example, pluractional verbs are formed by reduplication of the first part of a trisyllabic verb root. In this case, the initial tone of the verb melody spreads from right to left onto the reduplicated syllable, as in (39) and (40).

(39) *kàràntá:* ‘read’ → *kákkaràntá:* ‘read repeatedly’

(40) *tàmbájà:* ‘question’ → *tàntambájà:* ‘question repeatedly’

A replacive tonal melody also spreads from right to left. In example (41), the replacive melody of the Ventive marker -o: consists of a H toneme. This H toneme is assigned to the last syllable of the verb and extends to the first syllable erasing its lexical L toneme.

(41) /fíto:/

|fitá-o:\H|

go out-VEN

‘come out’

In example (42), the final L toneme of the replacive tonal melody H-L docks to the last syllable of the prosodic word, while the initial H toneme is assigned to the penultimate syllable of the prosodic word, then extends to its first syllable.

- (42) /ɾí:gunà:/
 |ɾì:gá:-una:\HL|
 gown.SG-PL
 ‘gowns’

In example (43), the two final H tonemes are assigned to two last syllables, while the first L toneme is assigned to the third syllable from the end and extends to the forth syllable from the end of the prosodic word.

- (43) /là:fiájjé:/
 |lá:fijá:-aC_fC_fe:\LHH|
 health-ABSTR
 ‘healthy’

6.1.2.6. Contour tone formation

When the number of tonemes in a tonal melody exceeds the number of syllables in a prosodic word, the first and second tonemes of the melody are mapped onto the first syllable of the prosodic word if this syllable is heavy, as in (44).

- (44) /zôbbá:/
 |zó:bè:-C_fC_fa:\HLH|
 ring-PL
 ‘rings’

6.1.2.7. Toneme deletion

If the initial syllable is light, it cannot host two tonemes of a melody. Thus, the first toneme of the melody is deleted (45).

- (45) /tʃí/
 |tʃí-\LH|
 eat-IMP
 ‘Eat!’

6.1.3. Floating tone attachment

Floating L tone is always added to the preceding syllable. Its realization varies depending on the preceding tone and the vowel length of the preceding syllable. When the root-final vowel to which the floating L tone is attached is short, this floating L tone is deleted, as in (46).

(46) ʔàukú ‘happen’ + ⁻¹wá: (NMLZ) → ʔàukúwá: ‘occurrence’

When the root-final long vowel carries L or a sequence of H and L, the floating L tone is deleted, see (47) and (48).

(47) ɽúfê: ‘close’ + ⁻¹wá: (NMLZ) → ɽúfê:wá: ‘closing’

(48) ɽfê: ‘say’ + ⁻¹wá: (NMLZ) → ɽfê:wá ‘saying’

When the root-final long vowel carries a H tone, the floating L tone gets linked, as in (49) and (50).

(49) káràntá: ‘read’ + ⁻¹wá: (NMLZ) → káràntá:wá: ‘reading’

(50) búllo: ‘appear’ + ⁻¹wá: (NMLZ) → búllô:wá: ‘appearance’ [H bullo][L o][H wa:]

6.1.4. Toneme deletion

A toneme can be deleted when its segmental carrier is deleted, as in (51) - (53). This toneme deletion is lexically determined, i.e. it takes place in specific lexemes.

(51) kásà ~ kás (not *kâs) ‘on the ground’

(52) máɽàʃín → máɽàs ‘lacking in’

(53) Háru:nà → Háru: (proper name)

6.1.5. LH contour simplification

Hausa does not have a rising contour on one syllable at the surface level. To avoid the realization of a LH sequence on one syllable, one of the two rules is applied: (i) the sequence of L and H becomes L if the preceding tone within the same word form is H, as in (54), and (ii) the sequence of L and H becomes H elsewhere, as in (55) and (56). LH contour simplification can be found in two cases: (i) two words are fused into one and (ii) when a segment is deleted while its H tone is retained and docks onto the preceding L-toned segment.

(54) múkà jí → múkài ‘we did’

(55) tà:wá → táu ‘mine’

(56) dò:mín → dón ‘because’

6.1.6. L toneme deletion

When the relativizer *dâ* gets integrated into the preceding prosodic word, the sequence of HL on the preceding syllable becomes H, as in (57) and (58). If there is a pause before the relativizer *dâ*, the sequence of HL on the preceding syllable is preserved. Both realizations are in free variation.

(57) *gída*: ‘house’ + *̀̀* DEF.MSC.SG + *dâ* ‘that’ → *gídandâ* ~ *gídân* # *dâ* ‘the house that...’

[H gidan][L da] ~ [H gida][L n][L da]

(58) *̀̀̀̀gá*: ‘gown’ + *̀̀* DEF.FEM.SG + *dâ* ‘that’ → *̀̀̀̀gárdâ* ~ *̀̀̀̀gâr* # *dâ* ‘the gown that...’

6.1.7. L tonal melody on the initial element of a noun phrase

In a number of compounds and noun phrases with titles borrowed from English, the initial element carries the L-toned melody, as in (59) - (61). The first L-toned element in compounds is typically a verb, however, a noun can be also found in this position. Note that the final vowel of the second element in compounds is commonly short.

(59) *̀̀̀̀ga*: *káfi* ‘prevention’ (*̀̀̀̀ga*: ‘precede’ + *káfi*: ‘securing’)

(60) *gà:ʃin* *bà:kí* ‘moustache’ (*gá:ʃi*: ‘hair’ + -n GEN + *bà:kí*: ‘mouth’)

(61) *Dòkta*: *Bá:džìrì* ‘Dr. Bargery’ (compare with *dóktà*: ‘doctor’)

The replacement of the lexical tonal melody of the initial element of a compound or a title noun phrase into the L tonal melody may point at the greater degree of formal integration of the noun phrase and compound elements, for example, by means of clitization of the initial element to the following noun, as suggested by Newman for title names (p.c.).

6.1.8. The rule of L tone raising

The rule of L tone raising postulates that word-final sequence of two L tones changes to LH if the final vowel is long, as demonstrated in (62). This rule was first mentioned by Leben (1971).

(62) *̀̀̀̀dì*: ‘blue (m.)’ + -a: FEM → *̀̀̀̀dìjà*: (the feminine marker copies the L tone of the preceding TBU) → *̀̀̀̀dìjá*: ‘blue (f)’ (final L-L change to L-H)

This rule has been a subject of discussion. One view is that this rule likely operated in the past and lacks strong evidence of its synchronic productivity (Newman & Jaggat 1989, Newman 2000: 611). Other view suggests that L tone raising “has never been a phonological rule. Rather, its origin is in a morphologically conditioned process which has left its mark in a

(nearly) absolute condition on the lexical prosody of words. This condition remains a valid generalization about modern Hausa” (Schuh 1989: 261).

6.2. Segmental rules

6.2.1. Superheavy syllable avoiding

When the definite marker *-n̄* appears after a long vowel, this long vowel becomes short, as in (63) and (64), and when it appears after a diphthong the final element of the diphthong is deleted, as in (65).

(63) wàndó: ‘trousers’ + *-n̄* (DEF.MSC.SG) → wàndôn ‘the trousers’

(64) sâ: ‘bull’ + *-n̄* (DEF.MSC.SG) → sân ‘the bull’

(65) mâi ‘oil’ + *-n̄* (DEF.MSC.SG) → mân ‘the oil’

6.2.2. Syllable nucleus deletion

Vowel-initial suffixes delete the nucleus of the final syllable of a root, as in (66) and (67). This nucleus can be of a monophthong or a diphthong.

(66) tá:g-o:gi: (tá:gà: ‘window.SG’-PL)

(67) mílij-o:ji: (mílijàn ‘million.SG’-PL)

6.2.3. Contraction

There are cases when a pronoun is suffixed to the preceding word form. In this case, the tone is usually (but not always) preserved, e.g. *zân ~ zá: n̄* (1SG.FUT) and (68).

(68)	a.	/ɾânkà	jà	dádê:/
		ɾâi-n-kà	jà	dádê:
		life-GEN.SG.MSC-2SG.MSC	3SG.MSC.SBJV	last_long_time

b.	/ɾânkài	dádê:/
	ɾâi-n-kà-jà	dádê:
	life-GEN.SG.MSC-2SG.MSC-3SG.MSC.SBJV	last_long_time
	‘May your life be lengthened.’	

7. Grammatical tones

Hausa has a tonal morpheme that has no segmental exponent, viz. imperative verb forms with a LH melody, as in (18), (24), (29), (40). In addition, Hausa has tonal morphemes that are combined with segmental exponents. They are the following:

- all nominal and adjectival plural affixes, e.g. noun root + -a:Ce:\HLH, see (30); noun root + -a:C_ɪa:\HLH; noun root + -C_ɪC_ɪa:\HLH, see (44); noun root + -a:C_ɪu:\HLH; noun root + -o:C_ɪi:\H, see (13) and (33); noun root + -a:C_ɪi:\H; noun root + -uCa:\HL, see (14); noun root + -uC_ɪa:\HL; noun root -aki:\LH or -a(i)ku:\LH, see (15); partially reduplicated noun root + -aki:\HLHH, see (18), noun root + -anni:\LH; noun root + -e:C_ɪani:\HLHH; noun root + -e:C₃aC_ɪi:\HLHH, noun root + -i:\LH; noun root + -u:\LH, see (38); noun root + -u:\H, see (69); noun root + -ai:\LH; noun root + -a:\H; noun root + -a:wa:\LH or -a:wa:\H, fully reduplicated noun root + -e:\LH, see (70).

(69) já:tsu: ‘fingers’ (já:tsà: ‘finger’ + -u:\H (PL))

(70) gìn-é gìn-é ‘buildings’ (gínì: ‘building’ + -e:\LH (PL))

- nominal derivative suffixes, e.g. noun/adjective/adverb root + -(VN)taka\LHL (abstract nouns); noun/adjective/adverb root + -(an)tɕi:\H (abstract nouns), see (71); noun/adjective/adverb root + -(Vn)tɕi:\HL (abstract nouns); verb root + -ajja:\LHL (nouns of mutuality and reciprocity); verb root + -e:C_ɪe:\LHH + nija: FEM (nouns of mutuality and reciprocity), see (21) and (22); verb root + -au\LH (nouns of human personality traits and habits), see (72); verb root + -e:\H (names of games and contests), see (73); ideophone root (not always attested separately) + -nija:\LHH (ideophonic sound and movement nouns), see (74).

(71) jáwantɕi: ‘majority’ (jáwà: ‘abundance’ + -(an)tɕi:\H)

(72) màntáú ‘forgetful person’ (mântá: ‘forget’ + -au\LH)

(73) tsállake ‘jumping game’ (tsálláká: ‘jump over’ + -e:\H)

(74) rùgumníjá: ‘rumbling noise’ (rùgum ‘noise of something rumbling’ + nija:\LHH)

- nominal derivative suffixes with prefixes: má- + verb root + -i:\LH (agentive masculine singular nouns); má- + verb root + -ija:\HLH (agentive feminine singular nouns); má- + verb root + -a:\LH (agentive plural nouns); ma- + verb root + -i:\H (instrumental masculine singular nouns); ma- + verb root + -ai:\LH (instrumental plural nouns); ma- + verb root + -a:\H (locative feminine singular nouns), see (75); ma- + verb root + -i:\H (locative masculine singular nouns); ma- + verb root + -ai:\LH (locative plural nouns).

(75) mǎtʃíjǎ: ‘small roadside place (for snacks)’ (ma- (LOC) + tʃí ‘eat’ + -a:\H (FEM.LOC))

- adjectival derivative suffixes, e.g. verb root + -aC_fC_fe:\LHH (masculine singular past participle adjectives); verb root + -aC_fC_fe:\LHH (masculine singular past participle adjectives); verb root + -aC_fC_fi:\LHH + -á: FEM (feminine singular past participle adjectives); verb root + -aC_fC_fu\LH (plural past participle adjectives); partially reduplicated verb root + -a:\LHH (intensive sensory adjectives), as in (76), (16) and (37).

(76) bǐjǎjǐjǎ: ‘disciplined (f.)’ (bí ‘follow’ + -aC_fC_fi:\LHH (PST.PART) + -á: (FEM))

- verbal derivative suffixes, e.g. verb root + -o:\H (ventive verbs), verb root + -a\HL or \HLH (applicative verbs), verb root + -e\HL or \HLH (Totality-Conclusive verbs), as in (77) and (12).

(77) sǎjè: ‘buy up/all’ (sǎjǎ: ‘buy’ + e:\HL (APPL))

- object suffixes, e.g. verb root + -ar\H (indirect object suffix), see (78); verb root + -e\LH (pronominal direct object suffix); verb root + -i\LH (nominal direct object suffix).

(78) sǎjǎr ‘buy’ (sǎjǎ: ‘buy’ + -ar\H)

- exclamations of contempt/dismissiveness: noun/verb/adverb/pronoun/ideophone/quantifier root + -o:\H (+mǎtà ‘to her’), as in (79).

(79) kǎmfo: mǎtà ‘the hell with the underpants!’ (kǎmfai ‘underpants’ + -o:\H + mǎtà ‘to her’)

- forming converbs, e.g. verb root + -e\LH (deverbal adverbial statives), as in (80) and (81).

(80) dǎfè ‘cooked’ (dǎfǎ: ‘cook’ + -e\LH (CONV))

(81) à ʔàikatʃé ‘in practice’ (à ‘in’ + ʔáikì: ‘work (n.)’ + -àtà: (verbalizer) + -e\LH (CONV))

8. Tonal classes of words

Finite verbs in Hausa are subdivided into eight classes. In Hausa studies they are labelled as Grades, from Grade 0 to Grade 7. This distinction is based on phonological features of verbs, namely, their tonal melody and their final vowel, as outlined in Table 5. In addition, these classes have specific semantic and syntactic correlates, e.g. all verbs of Grade 5 are transitive and express the efferential meaning (see Jaggar 2001: 214).

Note that the phonological features in Table 5 are given for verbs in their A (citation) form. This form implies that a verb is not followed by any object.

Table 5. Verb grades for Form A

Grade number	Tonal melody(s)	Final vowel(s)	Example
Grade 0	H	-í or -á	jí 'do'
Grade 1	HL or HLH	-á: or -à: (root-final vowel) -a: (Applicative)	g ^l á:ɾà: 'repair' dʒé:fà: 'throw on'
Grade 2	LH or LHL	-á: or -à: (root-final vowel) -a: (Partitive)	sàjá: 'buy' àikàtà: 'partly finish'
Grade 3	LH or LHL HH HL	-á or -à (root-final vowel) -a (root final vowel) -i, -a, -u (root final vowel)	nùkà 'become ripe' tú:bá 'repent' fá:dí 'fall'
Grade 4	HL or HLH	-e: (Totality-Conclusive)	kámmàlé: 'finish up'
Grade 5	H	-ar (Efferential)	áurár 'marry off'
Grade 6	H	-o: (Ventive-Centripetal)	kómó: 'come back'
Grade 7	LH	-u (Affected-subject)	ʃɪnfidú 'be well spread out'

A tonal melody on verbs belonging to one grade varies depending on the number of syllables, e.g. Grade 2 verbs *sàjá:* 'buy' (LH) and *tàimákà:* 'help' (LHL), see 6.1.2.4. The final vowel can be part of a root, as in *g^lá:ɾà:* 'repair', or it can be a derivative morpheme, as in *dʒé:fà:* 'throw on' (*dʒè:fá:* 'throw at' + *-à:\HL* (APPL)).

In addition, verb classes take different forms depending on the type of object it is followed by, viz. pronominal direct object (form B), nominal direct object (form C) and indirect object (form D). For example, A-forms of Grade 1 have the HL / HLH melody and the final vowel *-a:*. When they are followed by a nominal direct object (form C), they are used with the suffix *-a* that assigns the replacive grammatical tonal melody HL or HLL (depending on the number of syllables), e.g. *kámmàlá:* 'complete' (Grade 1, form A) and *kámmàlà* 'complete (something)' (Grade 1, form C). A similar situation occurs with verbs of Grade 2, which have the tonal melody LH / LHL and the final vowel *-a:* in the form A and the suffix *-i\LH* in form C, e.g. *tàmbájà:* 'ask' and *tàmbají* 'ask (someone)'.

9. Diachrony of tones

A discussion on the diachrony of tones in Hausa can be found in (Newman 2022).

10. Tonal notation

In practical orthographies, both in Nigeria and in Niger, tonal notation is lacking. In scientific description on Hausa, authors commonly use an orthography where long vowels are indicated by a macron (e.g. *sūnā* ‘name’), low tone is indicated by a grave accent, e.g. *màtfe* ‘woman’. Falling tone is designated by a circumflex, e.g. *mântā* ‘forget’. When a falling tone occurs on an open syllable, a circumflex indicates falling tone and vowel length, e.g. *sû* ‘fishing’. High tone is left unmarked, e.g. *ido* ‘in the eye’, *sūnā* ‘name’, *ɾàgō* ‘ram’, *fuskà* ‘face’ (Newman 2000: 3).

In this report, I use the following symbols and diacritics: a long vowel is marked as /a:/, a H tone by an acute accent, e.g. /á/, /á:/ or /ái/; a L tone by a gravis, e.g. /à/, /à:/ or /ài/; a sequence of H and L by a circumflex, e.g. /â:/ or /âi/. A tonal diacritic is given only on the first vowel of a tonal span.

11. Annotated text 1

This text is on Hausa of Zaria published by Bernard Caron in the CorpOrAn archive (Caron 2013). Speakers are Fatima Idriss and Hadiza Yakubu. The translation of the text was conducted by Marvellous S. Davan.

Below is a fragment of this text, where I have adapted the tonal notation (the original text follows the traditional Hausa tonal notation, see Section 10), and indicated the replacive tonal melodies in the morphophonological transcription (first line from the top). This version of the text also includes the second level of annotation that marks tonal spans, morae, and syllable boundaries. This fragment comprises 100 syllables.

hm:	ʔàk ^w ái	wáta	ɾá:na:
[L hm:]	[L ʔa][H .k ^w a,i]	[H wa.ta]	[H ɾa,a.na,a]
Mm	COP	some.FEM	day
‘Mm... One day,’			

múkà jí-o:\H léttì:
 [H mu][L .ka] <[H ji-.wo,o]> [H le,t][L .ti,i]
 1PL.PFV.FOC do-VEN late
 ‘we were late.’

séi ?ákà tsárè: mú léttì: hákà
 [H se,i] [H ?a][L .ka] [H tsa][L .rɛ,e] [H mu] [H le,t][L .ti,i] [H ha][L .ka]
 then 4.PFV.FOC block 1PL late like_this
 ‘Then they blocked us for being late.’

séi má:lámí:-n̄n já zó:
 [H se,i] [H ma,a][L .la][H .mi][L -,n] [H ja] [H zo,o]
 then teacher-DEF 3SG.MSC.PFV.FOC come
 ‘Then the teacher came’

já dù:ká:-e:\LH mu
 [H ja] <[L du,u][H .k-e,e]> mu
 3SG.MSC.PFV.FOC beat-ACC 1PL
 ‘and beat us.’

séi wáni já
 [H se,i] [H wa.ni] [H ja]
 then some.MSC 3SG.MSC.PFV.FOC
 ‘Then somebody ...’

já gáni: ?án tʃê:
 [H ja] [H ga] [H ?a,n] [H tʃe][L ,e]
 3SG.MSC.PFV.FOC see IMPS.PFV.NFOC say
 ‘heard that they said’

yá:-n ?és?ès hákà sù ʃígá ?áçì:
 [H yá-,n] [H ?e,s][L .?e,s] [H ha][L .ka] [L su] [L ʃi][H .ga] [H ?a][L .çì,i]
 children-GEN SS like_this 3PL.SBJV enter classroom
 ‘the pupils of SS should go into their class.’

séi já tʃê:
 [H se,i] [H ja] [H tʃe][L ,e]
 then 3SG.MSC.PFV.FOC say
 ‘Then he said’

tò: ʃí: má: báɾi:\LH jà tàfí
 [L to,o] [H ʃi,i] [H ma,a] <[L ba][H .ɾi]> [L ja] [L ta][H .fi]
 well 3SG.MSC even leave\IMP 3SG.MSC.SBJV go
 ‘well he should go’

dâ: má: ?à çí:nijo kílãs jákè:
 [H da][L ,a] [H ma,a] [L ?a] [H çì,i.ni.jo] [H ki.la,a.s] [H ja][L .ke,e]
 formerly even at junior class 3SG.MSC.IPFV.FOC
 ‘because he was in junior class.’

jí: kè: nán
 [H ʃi,i] [L ke,e] [H na,n]
 3SG.MSC COP.FOC ANAPH
 ‘That’s it.’

séi ʔákà tʃê: mut# ##
 [H se,i] [H ʔa][L .ka] [H tʃe][L ,e] ###
 then IMPS.PFV.FOC say [unintelligible]
 ‘Then they told us t...’

sáur̩a:-h̩ dúk sù tàttafí ʔáɕì:
 [H sa,u.ɾa][L -,n] [H du,k] [L su] [L ta,t.ta][H .fi] [H ʔa][L .ɕi,i]
 remainder-DEF all 3PL.SBJV go.PLAC classroom
 ‘all the others should go to their class.’

séi ʔákà tʃê: jà tsájà:
 [H se,i] [H ʔa][L .ka] [H tʃe][L ,e] [L ja] [H tsa][L .ja,a]
 then IMPS.PFV.FOC say 3SG.MSC.SBJV stop
 ‘Then they said he should stay,’

ʔà dù:ká:-e:\LH ʃi
 [L ʔa] <[L du,u][H .k-e,e]> ʃi
 IMPS.SBJV beat-ACC 3SG.MSC
 ‘they will beat him.’

12. Annotated text 2

This text is in Maradi Hausa, written by Hadiza Nazal and transcribed by Claude Gouffe (Nazal & Gouffe 1990). It is part of INALCO's teaching materials prepared for the 1990-1991 academic year.

Below is a fragment of this text, where I have adapted the tonal notation (the original version follows the traditional Hausa tonal notation, see Section 10) within the morphophonological transcription (first line from the top). Besides, I have added an annotation with tonal spans, morae, and syllable boundaries (second line from the top), as well as glosses and free translation. This fragment includes 107 syllables.

kà:fín	ʔà	sâ:	ʔámarjá:	lállè:
[L ka,a][H .fi,n]	[L ʔa]	[H sa][L ,a]	[H ʔa.ma,ɾ][H .ja,a]	[H la,l][L .le,e]
before	IMPS.SBJV	apply	bride	henna

‘Before applying henna on a bride,’

sái	ʔán	ɕé:	ʔán	tàmbájà:-i\LH
[H sa,i]	[H ʔa,n]	[H ɕe,e]	[H ʔa,n]	<[L ta,m.ba][H .j-i]>
then	IMPS.PFV.NFOC	go	IMPS.PFV.NFOC	ask-ACC

‘one goes and asks’

ráʔàjí:-n	wáni	má:lámí:
[H ra][L .ʔa][H .ji,-n]	[H wa.ni]	[H ma,a][L .la][H .mi,i]
opinion-GEN	some.MSC	scholar

‘the opinion of a scholar’

dón	ʔà	sán	ló:kàtʃi:-n	dà
[H do,n]	[L ʔa]	[H sa,n]	[H lo,o][L .ka][H .tʃi,-n]	[L da]
for	IMPS.SBJV	know	moment-GEN	REL

‘to know the moment when’

tá^f fǐ sáʔà:
 [H ta,f] [H fi] [H sa][L .ʔa,a]
 3SG.FEM.PFV.FOC exceed luck
 ‘she (the bride) will be luckiest.’

ʔín já:
 [H ʔi,n] [H ja,a] tʃè:
 [L tʃe,e] dà ʔàsubâ:
 [L da] [L ʔa.su][H .ba][L ,a] ne:
 if IMPS.PFV.NFOC say with morning COP
 ‘If he says that in the morning’

tá^f fǐ sáʔà:
 [H ta,f] [H fi] [H sa][L .ʔa,a]
 3SG.FEM.PFV.FOC exceed luck
 ‘she is the luckiest,’

sái ʔà fá:ʔà sâ:
 [H sa,i] [L ʔa] [H fa,a][L .ʔa] [H sa][L ,a] tá lállè:
 [H ta] [H la][L .le,e]
 then IMPS.SBJV begin put 3SG.FEM henna
 ‘then they should start applying henna on her.’

ʔà ló:kàtʃí:-n nán ʔín kò:
 [L ʔa] [H lo,o][L .ka][H .tʃi][L -,n] [H na,n] [H ʔi,n] [L ko,o] já:
 [H ja,a] tʃè:
 [L tʃe,e]
 in moment-DEF PROX if or 3SG.MSC.PFV.NFOC say
 ‘If this time he says’

màgarúbà: tá: fí
 [L ma.ga][H .ru][L .ba,a] [H ta,a] [H fi]
 sunset 3SG.FEM.PFV.NFOC exceed
 ‘is sunset when she is the luckiest’

sáí ?à zà:ḡá:-i\LH màgarúbà:
 [H sa,i] [L ?a] <[L za,a][H .ḡ-i]> [L ma.ga][H .ru][L .ba,a]
 then IMPS.SBJV choose-ACC sunset
 ‘then choose the sunset.’

dó:lè ?à zà:ḡá:-i\LH tsàkà:nín ?àsubâ:
 [H do,o][L .le] [L ?a] <[L za,a][H .ḡ-i]> [L tsa][H .ka,a][H .ni,n] [L ?a.su][H .ba][L ,a]
 necessary IMPS.SBJV choose-ACC between morning
 ‘It is necessary to choose between the morning’

dà màgarúbâ:
 [L da] [L ma.ga][H .ru][H .ba][L ,a] [H sa][L .bo,o][L .da]
 and sunset:? because
 ‘and the sunset because’

bâ: ?á ?íjà sâ: ?ámarjá: lállè:
 [H ba][L ,a] [H ?a] [H ?i][L .ja] [H sa][L ,a] [H ?a.ma,r][H .ja,a] [H la,l][L .le,e]
 NEG.IPFV IMPS.IPFV.NEG can apply bride henna
 ‘it is not possible to apply henna on the bride’

dà rá:na
[L da] [H ra,a.na]
with day
'during the day.'

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List of abbreviations and symbols

\	replacive tonal melody
-	affix
#	pause
AGT	Agentive
C	the copy of the last consonant of a root
C ₁	the first consonant of a root
C ₂	the second consonant of a root
C ₃	the third consonant of a root
C _f	the final consonant of a root
CONV	converb
COP	copula
ABSTR	abstract affix
ACC	accusative
ANAPH	anaphora
DEF	definite
DIST	distal demonstrative
EXCM	exclamation
(f.)	feminine
FEM	feminine
FOC	focus
GEN	genitive
H	high tone
IMP	imperative

IMPS	impersonal
INSTR	instrumental
INT	intensive sensory
IPFV	imperfective
L	low tone
(m.)	masculine
MSC	masculine
(n.)	noun
NEG	negation
NFOC	non-focus
NMLZ	nominalization
O	object
PFV	perfective
PL	plural
PLAC	pluractional
PROX	proximal demonstrative
PST.PTCP	past participle
RECP	reciprocal
REL	relativizer
Q	question
SBJV	subjunctive
SG	singular
TBU	tone-bearing unit
VEN	ventive